

SCIENTIFIC CLASSIFICATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS**Otamurodova Feruza Ergashevna****Samarkand State University of Architecture****English teacher**

Annotation: This article deals with important information about classification of phraseological units according to different scholars. On the other hand, theories and its examples were given in the work.

Key words: Phraseology, linguistics however, notably morphology, syntax, semantics and discourse, multi-word units

Phraseology is a comparatively young field of linguistics which has only relatively recently become established as a self-contained linguistic discipline. Phraseology is pervasive in all language fields. Phraseology is studying phraseological units (set expressions, phraseologisms, or idioms (in foreign linguistics). Phraseological units differ from free word-groups semantically and structurally:

1) they convey a single concept and their meaning is idiomatic, i.e. it is not a mere total of the meanings of their components

2) they are characterized by structural invariability (no word can be substituted for any component of a phraseological unit without destroying its sense (to have a bee in one's bonnet (not cap or hat).

3) they are not created in speech but used as ready-made units. Unlike a word, a phraseological unit can be divided into separately structured elements and transformed syntactically (On the instant he was thinking how natural and unaffected her manner was now that the ice between them had been broken. (Th. Dreiser, 'An American Tragedy'). I... found this man in a kind of seizure, and went for help. This broke the ice between us, and we grew quite chatty, without either of us knowing the other's name. (H. Pollitt, 'Serving My Time').

The vocabulary of a language is enriched not only by words but also by phraseological units. Phraseological units are word-groups that cannot be made in the process of speech, they exist in the language as ready-made units. They are compiled in special dictionaries. The same as words phraseological units express a single notion and are used in a sentence as one part of it. American and British lexicographers call such units «idioms». We can mention such dictionaries as: L.Smith «Words and Idioms», V.Collins «A Book of English Idioms» etc. In these

dictionaries we can find words, peculiar in their semantics (idiomatic), side by side with word-groups and sentences. In these dictionaries they are arranged, as a rule, into different semantic groups. A free combination is a syntactical unit, which consists notional and form words, and in which notional words have the function of independent parts of the sentence. In a phraseological unit words are not independent. They form set-expressions, in which neither words nor the order of words can be changed. Free combinations are created by the speaker. Phraseological units are used by the speaker in a ready form, without any changes. The whole phraseological unit has a meaning which may be quite different from the meaning of its components, and therefore the whole unit, and not separate words, has the function of a part of the sentence.

Nowadays phraseology plays a central role in a wide range of linguistic disciplines such as lexicography, contrastive linguistics, psycholinguistics, foreign language learning and teaching and natural language processing. As phraseology has strong links with several other fields of linguistics however, notably morphology, syntax, semantics and discourse, linguists vary in their opinions as to which range of subtypes in accordance with their degree of semantic non-compositionality, syntactic fixedness, lexical restrictions and institutionalization of word combinations or multi-word units should be included in the field of phraseology. Compounds and grammatical collocations are cases in point. This difficulty in establishing what exactly falls under field of phraseology is compounded by the fact that phraseology is a dynamic phenomenon, and displays both synchronic and diachronic variations.

Phraseological units are classified in accordance with several criteria. In the classification proposed by acad. Vinogradov phraseological units are classified according to the semantic principle, and namely to the degree of motivation of meaning, i.e. the relationship between the meaning of the whole unit and the meaning of its components. Three groups are distinguished: phraseological fusions (сращения), phraseological unities (единства), phraseological combinations (сочетания).

1. Phraseological fusions are non-motivated. The meaning of the whole is not deduced from the meanings of the components: to kiss the hare's foot (опаздывать), to kick the bucket (сыграть в ящик), the king's picture (фальшивая монета)

2. Phraseological unities are motivated through the image expressed in the whole construction, the metaphores on which they are based are transparent: to turn over a new leaf, to dance on a tight rope.

3. Phraseological combinations are motivated; one of their components is used in its direct meaning while the other can be used figuratively: bosom friend, to get in touch with.

Prof. Smirnitsky classifies phraseological units according to the functional principle. Two groups are distinguished: phraseological units and idioms. Phraseological units are neutral, non-metaphorical when compared to idioms: get up, fall asleep, to take to drinking. Idioms are metaphoric, stylistically coloured: to take the bull by the horns, to beat about the bush, to bark up the wrong tree. Structurally prof. Smirnitsky distinguishes one-summit (one-member) and many-summit (two-member, three-member, etc.) phraseological units, depending on the number of notional words: against the grain (не по душе), to carry the day (выйти победителем), to have all one's eggs in one basket. Prof. Amosova classifies phraseological units according to the type of context. Phraseological units are marked by fixed (permanent) context, which can't be changed: French leave (but not Spanish or Russian). Two groups are singled out: phrasemes and idioms.

1. Phrasemes consist of two components one of which is phraseologically bound, the second serves as the determining context: green eye (ревнивый взгляд), green hand (неопытный работник), green years (юные годы), green wound (незажившая рана), etc.

2. Idioms are characterized by idiomacity: their meaning is created by the whole group and is not a mere combination of the meanings of its components: red tape (бюрократическая волокита), mare's nest (нонсенс), to pin one's heart on one's sleeve (не скрывать своих чувств).

Prof. Koonin's classification is based on the function of the phraseological unit in communication. Phraseological units are classified into: nominative, nominative-communicative, interjectional, communicative.

1. Nominative phraseological units are units denoting objects, phenomena, actions, states, qualities. They can be:

- a) substantive – a snake in the grass (змея подколотная), a bitter pill to swallow;
- b) adjectival – long in the tooth (старый);
- c) adverbial – out of a blue sky, as quick as a flash;
- d) prepositional – with an eye to (с намерением), at the head of.

2. Nominative-communicative units contain a verb: to dance on a volcano, to set the Thames on fire (сделать что-то необычное), to know which side one's bread is buttered, to make (someone) turn (over) in his grave, to put the hat on smb's misery (в довершение всех его бед).

3. Interjectional phraseological units express the speaker's emotions and attitude to things: A pretty kettle of fish! (хорошенькое дельце), Good God! God damn it! Like hell!

4. Communicative phraseological units are represented by proverbs (An hour in the morning is worth two in the evening; Never say “never”) and sayings. Sayings, unlike proverbs, are not evaluative and didactic: That’s another pair of shoes! It’s a small world.

Some linguists (N.N. Amosova, J. Casares) don’t include proverbs and sayings into their classifications. Others (I.V. Arnold, A.V. Koonin, V.V. Vinogradov) do, on the grounds that 1) like in phraseological units their components are never changed 2) phraseological units are often formed on the basis of proverbs and sayings (A drowning man will clutch at a straw → to clutch at a straw). In dictionaries of idioms the traditional and oldest principle for classifying phraseological units – the thematic principle – is used.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that the study of any foreign language is impossible without referring to phraseology, which represents one of the most difficult for learning language levels. Idioms — units of speech communication, therefore their study should be carried out with the help of communicative exercises, the content of which is the students' performance of speech acts in terms of real communication or similar to them. It is now commonly accepted that the people who want to master the English language must have knowledge about wide range of complex lexical in English as a foreign language learner. Obviously, in order to command a foreign language deeply, a learner should learn pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary. But the main of them is phraseological units. The English language is full of phraseological units. Obviously, idioms, phrases, phrasal verbs and set expressions, aphorisms, maxims, proverbs and sayings are the main units of any language, without them our language may seem shallow or boring. The ability to use phrasal expressions is a great sign of language. A well-educated person who is a treasurer of phraseology is transforming his mind into a rational, understandable, compact manner. That is why every culture, literate person, a student who wants to be fluent in the language, should use regular expressions in the tongue

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